

DiSSCo Transition Project

**Definition of a TRL6 Minimum Viable
Product of core infrastructure**

Work Package 3 Data Infrastructure & Core Services
Milestone 14

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Table of contents

List of abbreviations	5
1. Introduction	6
2. Aims of the MVP	7
3. Minimum required functionality	7
4. Selection of a representative set of data	9
5. Dependencies	10
6. Steps to create a TRL6 production environment	11
7. Infrastructure	12
8. Code Quality	13
9. Security	14
10. Operating the MVP Core Infrastructure	15
Appendix 1: harmonized properties for a digital specimen	17
Appendix 2: harmonized properties for a digital media object	21

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Executive Summary

This document outlines the Minimum Viable Product (MVP) for DiSSCo's core infrastructure. Components of the core infrastructure were already built up to Technical Readiness Level 4-5¹ with funding received from DiSSCo partners, in-kind contribution from Naturalis and through earlier EU-funded projects. A prototype is accessible at sandbox.dissco.eu. The MVP aims to advance this to Technical Readiness Level 6², and to demonstrate added value by providing functionality for data enrichment and improved usability. To achieve this, the MVP will not only include components of the core infrastructure but will also include the DiSSCover annotations portal as a web front-end to support annotations. The document describes the minimum functionality that needs to be provided by the MVP and measurements taken to ensure a highly available, trustworthy software product. The document also discusses data selection criteria and dependencies on external services that may affect the release of the MVP.

Keywords

DiSSCo, FAIR Digital Objects, Annotations, Machine Actionable, Data Infrastructure, Specimens, Digital Extended Specimen

¹ TRL 4-5: Proof of concept tested with Handle infrastructure

² TRL 6: Technology demonstrated in a relevant environment with a representative set of real data, with enough features to attract early-adopter users of the RI

List of abbreviations

AAI - Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
ABCD - Access to Biological Collection Data, a TDWG standard
API - Application Programming Interface
AWS - Amazon Web Services
CC-By, CC-0 - Creative Commons Licenses
COL - Catalog of Life
D - Deliverable
DiSSCo - Distributed System of Scientific Collections
DiSSCover - DiSSCo Annotations Portal
DSArch - Digital Specimen Architecture
DTP - DiSSCo Transition Project
DTR - Data Type Registry
DwC - Darwin Core, a TDWG standard
FAIR - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FDO - FAIR Digital Object
GDWG - Gesellschaft für wissenschaftlichen Datenverarbeiten mbH Göttingen, Germany
GRNET - National Infrastructures for Research and Technology, Greece
GUI - Graphical User Interface
iGA - DiSSCo interim General Assembly governing the DiSSCo preparation phase
JSON - JavaScript Object Notation
MS - Milestone
openDS - Open Digital Specimen specification
RI - Research Infrastructure
RFC - Request for Comments
ROR - Research Organization Registry
TAB - Technical Advisory Board
TDWG - Biodiversity Information Standards
W3C - World Wide Web Consortium
WADM - Web Annotation Data Model
WP - Work Package

1. Introduction

The purpose of this document is to define the Minimum Viable Product (MVP) of core infrastructure that will be delivered by Naturalis later in the project. The MVP is planned in the project for May 2025, although the aim is to deliver it earlier, already in 2024. If Naturalis can deliver it before November 2024 then this will benefit MS3.3, where a hackathon could develop additional machine annotation services in a sandbox environment (a copy of the core infrastructure with test data) and successful ones could be added to the MVP. The functionality to include in the MVP as described in this document is based on consultations with the DiSSCo Technical Advisory Board (independent experts) and with stakeholders: the National Nodes, the CETAF ISTC working group and project partners in WP3 and WP4.

Core infrastructure is defined in the project description as consisting of the following components:

- Digital Specimen Repository
- Persistent Identifier Infrastructure
- Data processing and publishing
- Authorisation and Authentication infrastructure (AAI)
- Indexing and API

The core infrastructure is also known as DSArch: Digital Specimen Architecture. The DiSSCo data infrastructure is distributed and consists of the core infrastructure + source systems (e.g. collection management systems) provided by the DiSSCo partners. While a GUI is not part of the core infrastructure, further work on DiSSCover GUI will be included in the MVP to provide an easy way for users to use the annotation capabilities of the core infrastructure. DiSSCover is one of the core end-user services that DiSSCo aims to provide which will make use of the core infrastructure.

The mentioned components and DiSSCover have already been in development up to TRL 4-5 through funding received from DiSSCo partners (iGA members) and Naturalis in-kind contribution, through Synthesys+ (AAI components), DiSSCo Transition (openDS datamodel) and through BiCIKL (Persistent Identifier Infrastructure and Digital Specimen Repository components). The core infrastructure is accessible through a sandbox (acceptance environment): `sandbox.dissco.tech`, which contains test data with test Handles instead of DOIs. The latest version under development is available at `dev.dissco.tech` (non-stable environment, for development use).

The main audience for this document is the DiSSCo development team, technical team and DiSSCo stakeholders interested in the plans for technical development of the DiSSCo core infrastructure. We will therefore not go into detail about the underlying concepts of the core infrastructure such as the FAIR Digital Object concept, the Digital (Extended) Specimen concept or the concept of machine actionability. More information about underlying concepts is available in earlier architectural documents, in particular relevant

are DPP D6.2 Implementation and construction plan of the core architecture³, Architectural overview documents⁴ and the RFC documents⁵.

2. Aims of the MVP

The aims of the MVP are to:

1. Advance from TRL 4-5 (proof of concept tested with Handle infrastructure) to TRL 6: Technology demonstrated in a relevant environment with a representative set of real data.
2. Provide a minimum set of features that show clear added value of the DiSSCo core infrastructure to attract early-adopter users of the RI.

The MVP should have a minimum set of functionality that is required for providing specimen data derived from DiSSCo partners source systems as Digital Specimen FDO, and to achieve the second aim it should:

- support data enrichment (through annotations), and
- provide improved data usability, which can be achieved through providing additional metadata, indication of MIDS levels and addition of persistent identifiers.

3. Minimum required functionality

To support data enrichment and provide improved data usability, the MVP needs to include:

- Provision of *machine actionable (in the context of FDO)*⁶ Digital specimens and digital media images
- A minimum set of harmonised data properties compliant with GBIF Unified Model (see also Appendix 1 and 2). Note that some properties are openDS specific and do not currently have a DwC or ABCD equivalent
- Support for processing of DwC and ABCD datasets
- Taxonomic backbone (COL based)
- Support for links to related or derived data (through entity-relationships)
- Persistent identifiers: Digital Specimen DOIs (including support for tombstoned digital specimens), ROR for affiliation data, ORCID for annotators, Handles for annotations.
- Fully functional annotation infrastructure that allows both humans and machine agents to create W3C WADM compliant annotations as FDOs
- MIDS indicator for digitisation completeness

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6832200>

⁴ <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1YLeGKXf5WqlybbeFyGQoGRVWV9dMPZnW>

⁵ <https://github.com/DiSSCo/openDS/issues?q=is%3Aissue+is%3Aclosed+rfc>

⁶ Machine actionability, in the context of FDO, represents the FDO Forum community's focus on architecting the FDO to maximize dynamic data accessibility, parsability, interpretability, understandability, and synthesizability by machines while minimizing or eliminating the need for human oversight." <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7825650>

- support for describing the specimen type beyond `dwc:basisOfRecord` (based on `ods:topicDiscipline`)
- Provenance data

This requires the core infrastructure to be able to harvest data from:

- Darwin Core Archives
- Biocase endpoints

The provision of a set of harmonised data into a single all-encompassing data specification (openDS) requires at the minimum support for Darwin Core terms and ABCD 2.06 terms (concepts), including EFG for earth science specimens, which is an ABCD extension. This is because DwC and ABCD(EFG) are the most prevalent bio- and geodiversity standards for specimens and openDS predominantly uses terms from these standards. The set of harmonised properties for the MVP will cover (most) terms in the openDS model for DwC and ABCD(EFG), estimated to be around 200 terms. The MVP will also harmonize some other properties, like `ods:topicDiscipline` which is needed to calculate a MIDS level and is not part of DwC or ABCD(EFG). Harmonizing terms from other standards is not part of the MVP but terms from other standards are included in the datamodel like terms from AudubonCore and DCterms to support digital media.

As part of the MVP, a DOI for each digital specimen will be created if a DOI is not already present for these in the DiSSCo infrastructure. DOIs for digital media objects are considered to be part of the MVP as these will provide clear added value, but may be excluded in the MVP if there is not enough budget to include them in DiSSCo's transition phase. While a download service for generated DOIs will not be part of the MVP, a download function is highly desirable to allow specimen hosts to include the DOIs in their local collection management system. This guards against duplicate digital specimens when local specimen identifiers are changed.

Fully functional annotation infrastructure means that users can annotate individual digital specimens and digital media objects, and machines can annotate individual digital specimens and digital media objects as well as annotate batches of these objects. Users will be supported with functionality to annotate through a user-friendly web interface. Fully functional also means that annotations should be possible at three different levels:

- Specific property (e.g. add a DwC term with a value)
- Specific class (e.g. add identification with its properties like `identifiedBy` and `dateIdentified`)
- Whole Digital Object.

The MVP will need to support users with a web interface to trigger Machine Annotation Services for one or multiple objects.

Since annotations require authenticated users, the MVP will need to include functionality for logging in and creating a user account. At a minimum, log in through an existing ORCID or Google account will be supported.

Other functionality that the MVP will include:

- A documented procedure for developers to easily add their own Machine Annotation Service to the DiSSCo infrastructure
- Public RESTful APIs for developers of other infrastructures as well as machine users of the data
- MIDS level calculation with MIDS level provided as information to the digital specimen, with support for all MIDS levels
- Authentication system for users who want to annotate
- Names will be resolved against a COL-based taxonomic backbone and this information will be included in the digital specimen data as part of the data ingestion and harmonisation process.
- Support for entity-relationships to link to other online data sources. Entity-relationships can be included in a digital specimen or other digital object in DiSSCo and expressed as: "has relationship with". The link to the referenced resource can be an internal object linked through the PID or an external object, for example a Catalogue of Life Name ID. An entity-relationship also contains information about the type of relationship and creator, see the [schema documentation](#).
- Uptime monitoring with a publicly available status page that shows past and present uptime of the core infrastructure components.

The public API will expose the full scope of digital specimen data with their media and annotations, so these could potentially already be used for round-tripping data with source systems, but that is not the focus of the MVP.

4. Selection of a representative set of data

The following criteria were used for the selection of datasets to include:

- the dataset should be from a DiSSCo partner
- the dataset should be already publicly available and under CC-BY or CC-0 license
- the dataset should be formatted as a Darwin Core Archive or be available in ABCD 2 through a BioCASE endpoint.
- the datasets together should contain specimens from some common taxonomic groups in Zoology, Botany, and also include specimens from Earth Geology and Astrogeology
- the datasets together should be big enough to show the infrastructure works at scale but small enough to keep the costs manageable, about 2M specimens in total*

- some of the datasets should contain linkable specimen images served through a IIIF compatible image server.

We randomly selected a number of datasets already during initial development and testing of the core infrastructure components that fit these criteria. This resulted in a representative set of data of approximately 2M specimens in total consisting of:

- Naturalis Biodiversity Center: Vermes, Lepidoptera, Crustacea
- Natural History Museum Denmark: Ornithology
- Freie Universität Berlin: Herbarium Berolinense
- Tallinn University of Technology: Geology & Paleontology collections

These datasets currently include 1.337.600 specimens and about 700,000 media objects, to stay under 2M we may need to exclude media objects of one of the datasets in the MVP. The MVP will also need to include the 24 digital specimens from Manchester University and Naturalis that already got a DOI (see:

<https://github.com/DiSSCo/dissco-developers-documentation/wiki/Digital-Specimen-DOIs-for-Jeremy's-Spider-publication>).

This selection of data will result in the following disciplines not being covered in the MVP: Microbiology, Ecology, Anthropology, Archeology, and also no coverage of living specimens or additional physical materials supporting the specimens such as slides, notebooks etc. As an alternative, it will therefore be investigated if we can include many more datasets but with a subset of records for each, to better account for the existing variability in implementations of data models and metadata. This is a "nice to have" and not a requirement for the MVP.

*To provide this set of data as Digital Specimens with DOIs, costs are involved for storing and processing the data but there are also significant costs for creating the DOIs through DataCite. Since a fee structure for minting large numbers of DOIs is still under discussion, we have to assume that we need to follow the current DataCite fees for the MVP, which is at the time of writing 13.000 Euro for up to 2M DOIs. A higher number would result in a higher tier, therefore we need to stay under 2M digital specimens and digital media objects to keep costs manageable.

5. Dependencies

The core infrastructure depends on a few external services:

- AAI infrastructure provided by [GRNet](#) and
- a Data Type Registry (DTR) to be provided by [GDWG](#) (needed for machine actionability in FDO context).
- DOI infrastructure
- AWS Cloud services
- ORCID, ROR

A Service Level Agreement cannot be created with GRNET until DiSSCo ERIC is established but we should aim for some uptime guarantees and support by GRNET. So far we had no

problems with uptime, however, support for changes was not always present. As a fallback scenario for AAI issues a Naturalis Keycloak could be used but then login with institutional accounts may not be possible. Login with institutional accounts will therefore not be a requirement for the MVP.

GWDC is planning to provide a DTR in time and migrate our type definitions with attributes from the ePIC test-DTR to this DTR. A peer review process for agreement on type definitions will not yet be in place but GWDC personnel will review our definitions. In case of issues, as a fallback scenario, we will cache type definition data. This is important to be able to mint new DOIs in case the DTR goes down.

While we use DataCite infrastructure we will not be dependent on it for operating the MVP as we only use it to store a copy of the DOI metadata. We rely on DOI infrastructure provided by CNRI such as the DOI proxy but provision of DOI infrastructure is guaranteed through agreements with DOIF and has been operational for over 20 years. For AWS Naturalis has contractual agreements as a client. ORCID and ROR have communities behind them to guarantee persistent and resolvable PIDs.

6. Steps to create a TRL6 production environment

a. Access

The core infrastructure should be reachable through: **<https://discover.dissco.tech>** which should direct to the DiSSCover annotation portal, and through **data.dissco.tech/api/** which should direct to the API. Orchestration services should be provided through: **orchestration.dissco.tech** (for authorized users). This domain is currently used for the sandbox environment, which will need to get another.

b. Support

User support will be managed through the DiSSCo JitBit helpdesk (dissco.jitbit.com). Support will be limited since the MVP is intended for early adopters and the DiSSCo helpdesk will not yet be fully operated by CETAF (CETAF has expressed interest in becoming the help desk service provider under DiSSCo operation). For the MVP therefore both first line as well as second and third line support will be assigned to the DiSSCo development team. In case the usage of the MVP results in more first-line support than the development team can handle, an alternative solution will be sought. This can either be through creating a FAQ, or by redirecting first-line support to Naturalis Support or to CETAF.

c. Documentation

The MVP will be accompanied by schema documentation for the implemented openDS datamodel, in schemas.dissco.tech. The public API will be documented through openAPI documentation and a beginner's guide to the API, following the BiCIKL technical interoperability [recommendations](#). The implemented MVP will be summarised in a deliverable document. A 'MAS cookbook' will be supplied as documentation for

developers who want to create a Machine Annotation Service, further guidance to create annotations will be provided through the DiSSCover annotations portal.

d. Testing

Functional testing and Acceptance testing for the DiSSCover GUI will be done with test scenarios, selected end-users will test the GUI in different roles following the scenarios. The scenarios can be found in a document⁷ that will be updated before each planned test cycle. Other types of testing will be done by the development team depending on anticipated needs for a reliable operation of the MVP. For details about code quality testing and automated test workflows see the chapter on code quality.

7. Infrastructure

The MVP for the core infrastructure will be supported by a technical infrastructure. For this, Naturalis chose an agnostic cloud-native approach, using Amazon Web Services (AWS) as its provider. For the implementation, Naturalis decided to use generic open-source structures where possible, provided as managed services by AWS. This provides the flexibility to change from cloud provider if necessary, while keeping the benefit that running in the cloud offers.

The infrastructure embraces a modern approach based on an event-driven architecture.⁸ This creates a flexible landscape of decoupled applications, enabling easy transition between different technologies or implementations. By creating stateless applications in combination with an event-driven architecture enables us to horizontally scale based on the system load. Essential for horizontal scalability is a flexible platform to run the services on. For this platform, Naturalis picked Kubernetes, an industry standard container orchestration service. With Kubernetes, we can easily scale out or scale in the required computation requirements in a completely automated way. This also can help DiSSCo run services as highly available services, as it is always possible to run multiple instances of any application.

By running regular automated health checks, Kubernetes automatically restarts machines or services whenever they become unavailable. We (the DiSSCo development team at Naturalis) will run Kubernetes as an AWS-managed service, AWS EKS, where AWS will be responsible for keeping up the platform and the DiSSCo development team is responsible for keeping up the applications.⁹

While a good choice in covering DiSSCo's flexible computational needs, running persistent storage on Kubernetes is generally seen as not being a good idea and the creators of Kubernetes recommend not to do it¹⁰. For the persistent storage of data, we will use AWS-managed data storage services. As explained in BiCIKL Deliverable 7.4, the core infrastructure uses three types of storage.¹¹ A Relational Database, using JavaScript Object

⁷ Test scenarios DiSSCover:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1Mq3qzxLyqva9LwyzBLlz2F3YeEs_FW-uaVBaUS8H-VA

⁸ DPP D6.1 (<https://doi.org/10.34960/366d-sf49>)

⁹ <https://aws.amazon.com/eks/> (visited 16-05-2024)

¹⁰ See:

<https://medium.com/@fengruohang/database-in-kubernetes-is-that-a-good-idea-daf5775b5c1f>

¹¹ BiCIKL D7.4, will be published on ARPHA Preprints after approval

Notation (JSON) columns, for the latest version of the data. To manage the database, including high availability and automated backups, we use AWS Relational Database Service (RDS).¹² In addition to a relational database, we also use a document database for the storage of provenance records. A document database scales better when we get hundreds of millions of provenance records. For this we plan to use AWS's DocumentDB, which will automatically scale to the requested load, and provide high availability and automated backups.¹³

By combining open source software with the managed implementation, we ensure that we will not run into the risk of vendor lock-in, but still benefit from the flexibility and scalability that the cloud provides.

8. Code Quality

Writing secure and highly-maintainable code is essential to the long-term success of DiSSCo. To ensure these non-functional requirements, we (the development team at Naturalis) implemented several checks to which the code needs to comply. Before any code is being included into the application, we will run a so-called Continuous Integration (CI) process, automated through Github Actions.

The first step in this process is a check on the Code Quality. SonarCloud is an industry standard tool for objectively checking the quality of code. SonarCloud uses a list of rules to which the code needs to apply. These rules are created through an open community process. For example, for Java the programming language DiSSCo uses for our data processing and backend applications, there are almost 700 rules, ranging from checks on hardcoded credentials, checks on OWASP issues such as SQL injection, to code complexity or minor bugs.

Sonar also checks our unit test coverage. We aim for a unit test coverage of at least 80%. This means that 80% of all lines, conditions and methods are covered by independently running tests. In addition to unit tests, we also implement integration tests which test the functionality between multiple components, such as an application and a data storage solution. An exception to this rule are the frontends, such as DiSSCover where we only run tests for data manipulation. The Sonar scores for DiSSCo infrastructure are publicly available and can be found <https://sonarcloud.io/organizations/dissco/projects>.

¹² <https://aws.amazon.com/rds/> (visited 16-05-2024)

¹³ <https://aws.amazon.com/documentdb/> (visited 16-05-2024)

Fig. 1. Shows the Sonar score for the DiSSCo Backend, which provides the APIs for DiSSCover. All non-functional requirements have the highest score, coverage in 93% of the code. We have one Accepted Issue as we encountered a false-positive in the Sonar checks.¹⁴

Next to Sonar code quality checks, we also run automated security checks on both the code, the container image and all libraries used in the project. We use a tool called Trivy for this process. Each time new code is proposed, we run all the security checks to see if we introduced any new vulnerabilities, but also to check existing code and libraries against new security issues. When a new vulnerability is encountered, Naturalis will do everything possible to mitigate this security issue. If it is impossible because it is part of a deeper dependency, and Naturalis is dependent on the supplier to fix the issue, we take note of it in the project to ensure we fix this when we next touch this project. Last but not least is a peer review by another programmer in the team. These so-called peer reviews are an essential part of the acceptance process. Not only does this create an additional layer of security and maintenance, it also ensures that knowledge about the code is shared across the team. When large or complicated pieces of code are being added, the developers involved will go through the code together to ensure the reviewer knows how the code is set up. The reviewer then provides feedback and requests the original author to incorporate the suggestions or respond to the questions. When all remarks have been resolved, the code can be accepted and become part of the application.

9. Security

Security is a vital part of any application which is publicly available over the internet. Both DiSSCover and the DiSSCo APIs need to be well protected. This means Naturalis will only provide access to these services over secure connections (HTTPS). In addition to a secure connection, Naturalis will also only accept certain TLS versions (at the moment TLS 2.0 or

¹⁴ https://sonarcloud.io/summary/overall?id=DiSSCo_dissco-core-backend (visited 16-05-2024)

up) and certain ciphers. We will follow the guidelines of the Dutch Cyber Security Center¹⁵ and the Naturalis guidelines. In addition to the TLS guidelines, we run several other security recommendations to keep up to date with the latest best practices. We check regularly that we score the highest security level with, for example SSL Labs.com.¹⁶ New security guidelines might mean that Naturalis will tighten its security, which could impact outdated browsers.

SSL Report: sandbox.dissco.tech (18.171.50.208)

Assessed on: Thu, 16 May 2024 09:01:01 UTC | [Hide](#) | [Clear cache](#)

[Scan Another »](#)

Fig. 2. Shows the SSL Labs Security score of sandbox.dissco.tech at 16-05-2024. The score of A+ is the highest available security score.

In addition to Web Security we also secure our infrastructure by using two-factor authentication on our infrastructure. In the case of individual servers, this means users need to whitelist their IP-address as well as supply their public key in the authorized keys of the server. When using Kubernetes, users will need to be authenticated through AWS (where we require a two-factor authentication) and the users need to be authorised to use the service. Within AWS we apply the principle of least privilege, meaning that users only get access to services required for their work.

10. Operating the MVP Core Infrastructure

The MVP is targeted to early adopters. The idea behind this is that early adopters have a clear use case for using the core infrastructure and are willing to work with the development team to optimise functionality to make the infrastructure fit for their needs. When this is successful, early adopters will likely advertise the infrastructure, thus contributing to its successful adoption. DiSSCo CSO and the technical team will identify early adopters and their use cases through discussions with stakeholders, e.g. in projects

15

<https://english.ncsc.nl/publications/publications/2021/january/19/it-security-guidelines-for-transport-layer-security-2.1> (visited 16-05-2024)

¹⁶ <https://www.ssllabs.com/ssltest/analyze.html?d=sandbox.dissco.tech> (visited 16-05-2024)

in which DiSSCo is involved or in discussions with national nodes. Early adopters may also be identified through user requests coming in via the DiSSCo helpdesk, GitHub, or info@dissco.eu. An overview of identified early adopters will be maintained in an internal list maintained by DiSSCo CSO and accessible also by the technical team to prioritize their support, for example with providing extra data or new functionality. Currently, there are four known use cases put forward:

1. Identification as a step in the digitisation of butterflies at Naturalis. Biological specimen records need to have a taxonomic identification to make it worthwhile to publish them online in GBIF or a local portal, as this makes them findable. The core infrastructure can provide annotation functionality for doing these identifications by experts, and makes it possible to involve external experts and get assistance by AI to make this more efficient. The Naturalis butterfly collection (Lepidoptera) will be included in the MVP.
2. Supporting virtual reference collections through additional functionality to create a virtual collection from digital specimens in the core infrastructure and add suitable specimen images showing certain traits for identification. Pilot reference collections are being created in the TETTRIs project. This use case will need two pilot datasets that are not yet available but are being worked on by Luomus: Serbian Eumerus hoverflies, and a set with the 100 most common European wild bee species. It may also need functionality to add additional images by users.
3. The museum of Vienna is interested in a pilot to use the infrastructure for supplying MIDS level 0 specimen data and improving the MIDS level to see how this can be used in their digitisation strategy.
4. Citizen science platforms DoeDat and Herbonauten are interested in connecting with the core infrastructure to use machine annotation services for pre-selecting specimen images for digitisation missions based on criteria such as printed versus written labels and language of the label data. The platforms would like to supply digitized information as enrichment to the digital specimen records in the core infrastructure. This use case requires further implementation of virtual collections and exchange of data with these platforms.

The MVP will need to provide a stable environment for working with digital specimens. While the core infrastructure is designed as a high-available service (see Infrastructure chapter), some downtime is acceptable until full operation of the infrastructure as the MVP is mainly serving early adopters. This means that the MVP can be operated and supported by the DiSSCo development team and be supported only during Naturalis office hours.

Appendix 1: harmonized properties for a digital specimen

see for the JSON schema, version 0.1.0:

<https://schemas.dissco.tech/schemas/digitalobjects/0.1.0/digital-specimens/digital-specimen.json>

Property	Type	Description	Example
ods:id	string	The unique digital identifier of the object	" https://doi.org/10.22/XXX-XXX-XXX "
ods:version	integer	The version of the object, each change generates a new version	1
ods:created	string	The timestamp that the object version was created in DiSSCo	"2023-10-02T12:31:34.806Z"
ods:type	string	The FDO type of the object	
ods:midsLevel	integer	The MIDS level of the object, see MIDS	0
ods:normalisedPhysicalSpecimenId	string	The physical specimen identifier of the object. When locally unique this is a combination between source-system-id and the local identifier	
ods:physicalSpecimenId	string	The physical specimen identifier of the object. Taken over as-is	

ods:physicalSpecimenIdType	string	To indicate if the physical identifier is globally unique or locally unique	"Resolvable"
ods:topicOrigin	string	The topic origin of the specimen	"Natural"
ods:topicDomain	string	The topic domain of the specimen	"Life"
ods:topicDiscipline	string	The topic discipline of the specimen	"Botany"
ods:markedAsType	boolean	The specimen is marked as a type specimen	
ods:hasMedia	boolean	Indicates if there are any media objects attached to this specimen	
ods:specimenName	string	The accepted specimen name of the digital specimen	"Roptrocerus typographi (Györfi, 1952)"
ods:sourceSystem	string	The handle to the source system object which retrieved the data from the CMS	"https://hdl.handle.net/20.5000.1025/XXX-XX-XXX"
ods:livingOrPreserved	string	Whether the specimen is living or preserved	"Living"
dcterms:license	string	License for the metadata of the physical specimen	
dcterms:modified	string	Modification date for specimen information	

dwc:basisOfRecord	string	The basis for the record	
dwc:preparations	string	DwC term	"fossil"
dwc:disposition	string	DwC term	"in collection"
dwc:institutionCode	string	DwC term	"MNF"
dwc:institutionId	string	ROR or Wikidata identifier, based on DwC term	" https://ror.org/015hz7p22 "
dwc:institutionName	string	Full museum name according to ROR or Wikidata	"National Museum of Natural History"
dwc:collectionCode	string	DwC term	"EBIRD"
dwc:collectionId	string	DwC term	" https://www.gbif.org/grscicoll/collection/fbd3ed74-5a21-4e01-b86a-33d36f032d9c "
dwc:informationWithheld	string	DwC term	"location information not given for endangered species"
dwc:dataGeneralizations	string	DwC term	"Coordinates generalized from original GPS coordinates to the nearest half degree grid cell."
dwc:ownerInstitutionId	string	ROR or Wikidata identifier for the owning institution	" https://ror.org/03wkt5x30 "

dwc:recordedBy	string	DwC term	"José E. Crespo"
dwc:recordedById	string	DwC term	" https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1825-0097 "
dwc:datasetName	string	DwC term	"Hummingbirds"
dcterms:accessRights	string	DC term	"not-for-profit use only"
dcterms:rightsHolder	string	DC term	"Museu de História Natural e da Ciência da Universidade do Porto"
materialEntity	array	Array of Material Entity	
dwc:identification	array	Array of Identification	
assertions	array	Array of Assertions	
occurrences	array	Array of Occurrences	
entityRelationships	array	Array of Entity Relationships	
citations	array	Array of Citations	
identifiers	array	Array of Identifiers	
chronometricAge	array	Array of Chronometric Age	
agents	array	Array of Agents	

Required properties: "ods:id", "ods:version", "ods:type", "ods:created", "ods:midsLevel", "ods:physicalSpecimenId", "ods:physicalSpecimenIdType", "ods:sourceSystem", "dcterms:license", "dwc:institutionID"

Appendix 2: harmonized properties for a digital media object

see for the JSON schema, version 0.1.0:

<https://schemas.dissco.tech/schemas/digitalobjects/0.1.0/digital-media-objects/digital-entity.json>

Property	Type	Description	Example
ods:id	string	The unique digital identifier of the object	"https://hdl.handle.net/20.5000.1025/XXX-XXX-XXX"
ods:version	integer	The version of the object, each change generates a new version	1
ods:created	string	The timestamp that the object version was created in DiSSCo	
ods:type	string	The FDO type of the object	
dcterms:type	string	DC term	"Image"
ac:accessUri	string	Access URI	
dwc:institutionId	string	ROR or Wikidata identifier, based on DwC term	" https://ror.org/015hz7p22 "

dwc:institutionName	string	Full museum name according to ROR or Wikidata	"National Museum of Natural History"
xmpRights:webStatement	string	Adobe XMP term	
dcterms:format	string	DC term	
dcterms:license	string	DC term	
dcterms:description	string	DC term	
dcterms:rights	string	DC term	
??? :rightsUri	string	Rights URI, format URI	
dcterms:accessRights	string	DC term	
dcterms:rightsHolder	string	DC term	
dcterms:source	string	DC term	
??? :sourceUri	string	Source URI, format URI	
dcterms:creator	string	DC term	

dcterms:created	string	DC term	
dcterms:modified	string	DC term	
assertions	array	Array of Assertions	
citations	array	Array of Citations	
identifiers	array	Array of Identifiers	
entityRelationships	array	Array of Entity Relationships	
agents	array	Array of Agents	

Required properties: "ods:id", "ods:version", "ods:created", "ac:accessUri", "dcterms:license"